

This paper is supplemental material for the publication of case study in *Journal of Hydraulics*.

1. Hydrographs

Different hydrographs are obtained from a recent hydrological study (Bruland, 2020) of the flash flood in Storelva river. In the paper, the author tried to reenact the extreme event on the 24th of July, 2017, and to simulate seven different hydrographs with different rainfall intensities. Four more hydrographs were obtained from the hydrograph finally proposed for the event on the 24th of July, 2017. In this case, peak discharge values were modified. The mass conservation errors in the 4 modified hydrographs are less than 1%, and time to peak errors are less than 3%. These modified hydrographs were in accordance with the tolerance range proposed in Bruland (2020). As recommended in Chu et al. (2020), 10 different hydrographs, excluding the original one, were used for the simulation of IBER, which is the preparation step for the 1D CNN training dataset. The original hydrograph was used for the simulation of IBER+.

Figure 1. Hydrograph for the flood event in Utvik (2017)

Note: All the other hydrographs resulted from virtualization of the original hydrograph presented in Bruland (2020). Combo 1, Combo 2, Combo 3, and Combo 4 are modified based on the hydrograph chosen for the prediction. Q_143, Q_164, Q_180, Q_200, Q_224, and Q_242 were courtesy of O. Bruland.

2. The terminologies and theoretical concepts of 1D CNN models

2.1 Preprocessing data

X_values(input) for training data are 10 sets of the hydrograph, which have an interval of 3600 seconds, and Y_values(output) were inundation maps from IBER+, linearly interpolated into raster data with 300 seconds interval time series. As the number of input should be the same as that of output, linear interpolation was used for the training dataset. The input was sequenced before being put into the 1D CNN models, as the model needs to do some regression analysis easier. The size of the sequence is 3, which means $X(t-2)$, $X(t-1)$, $X(t)$ were needed as the input, and $Y(t)$ was needed as the output. The output dataset has no information of water depth in the none floodplain. This is logical since pixels not classified as floodplain or river channel would not have information of water depth changes in time series. These missing values would affect the learning process badly as it would result in the unstable performance of loss function and eventually deteriorate the performance of the ANN model(Gill et al., 2007). Once the missing values were substituted with 0, then the activation function was expected to be saturated so quickly(Rashid, 2016). For these reasons, the missing values in the output dataset were changed to very small positive values. For the validation process, 70% of the training dataset was used for the training, and 30% of the training dataset was for the validation.

2.2 1D Convolutional Neural Network

1D Convolutional Neural Network (1D CNN) is a modified version of the 2D Convolutional Neural Network(2D CNN). The differences between them are the dimension of the inputs, kernels, and feature maps. CNN's differ from Fully Connected Network(FCN), where all the neurons are fully connected to each other. CNNs have sparse connections and allow parameter sharing. The sparse connection is advantageous when analyzing thousands of pixels, such as image classification. The kernel in CNN might detect small, hundreds of meaningful features, out of thousands or millions of pixels. It would spare the memory(Goodfellow Yoshua Bengio et al., 2016; Rautela & Gopalakrishnan, 2020) and training time. Parameter sharing works in a way that the value of weight applied to one input is tied to the value of the weight, applied to other inputs. Unlike, FCN which is learning a separate set of parameters at every location, CNN would use each member of the kernel at every position, saving memory requirement and statistical

efficiency(Goodfellow Yoshua Bengio et al., 2016). The output of the layer in 1D CNN is shown in Equation(Kiranyaz et al., 2019) (2):

$$y_k^l = f(b_k^l + \sum_{i=1}^{N^{l-1}} Conv\ 1D(w_{ik}^{l-1}, s_i^{l-1})) \quad (2)$$

where y_k^l is the output of the layer l, s_i^{l-1} is the output of i^{th} neuron of layer l-1, and w_{ik}^{l-1} is the kernel weight from i^{th} neuron of layer l-1, connected to k^{th} neurons at layer l, b_k^l is the scalar bias of the k^{th} neuron of layer l, and $f(\dots)$ is the activation function within the layer.

2.3 Activation function

Activation function is a transformation technique to make neuron in ANN deactivate or activate to let itself decide whether to pass the information. Leaky Rectified Linear Unit(LReLU) was used for this study. The mathematical expression of LReLU is described in Formula (3):

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} x & x > 0 \\ 0.01x & otherwise \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

LReLU has non-zero gradient over the entire domain, tackling the fact that Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) gets negative input, it is saturated with zero gradients. The quick saturation with zero gradients might be problematic when there is no learning process, as a gradient-based optimization algorithm is used. LReLU does however activate when a small, non-zero negative gradient passes through and is expected to solve the saturation problem(Bai et al., 2018; Kiranyaz et al., 2019; Maas et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2018). LReLU was employed in the 1D CNN layer, the dense layer, and the output layers.

2.4 Batch Normalization (BN)

Batch Normalization(BN) is applied to convert the distribution of the inputs to a standard normal distribution with a mean of 0, and a variance of 1. Normally, the convergence of a convolutional neural network is getting slower due to the fact that the distribution of inputs, hidden layer after hidden layer, reaches the limits of the activation function, being saturated. BN ensures that the distribution of the input is within a sensitive range of the activation function, leading the input to a large action of the loss function. BN is known to make the training process faster(Ioffe & Szegedy, 2015; Wang et al., 2020).

BN is described mathematically in Formulas from 4 to 7 (Ioffe & Szegedy, 2015; Wang et al., 2020). Input $[x_i]$ in Formula (4), and output $[y_i]$ in Formula (7) are in a mini-batch, with $i \in [1, 2, 3, \dots, m]$. In Formula (4), mini-batch mean μ_B calculates, then in Formula (5), mini-batch variance σ_B^2 calculates. Then in Formula (6), the input $[x_i]$ is normalized, and it leads to the output y_i in Formula (7).

$$\mu_B = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m x_i \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_B^2 = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (x_i - \mu_B)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\hat{x}_i = \frac{x_i - \mu_B}{\sqrt{\sigma_B^2 + \epsilon}} \quad (6)$$

$$y_i = \gamma \hat{x}_i + \beta \equiv BN_{\gamma, \beta}(x_i) \quad (7)$$

where ϵ in Formula (5) is a small positive number for divisor to be zero, and γ and β in Formula (6) are the parameters to be learned throughout backpropagation.

2.5 Dropout

Dropout is a way to improve the neural network. The idea is to dropout random hidden units, that are breaking up the part of the neural network connections. When dropout is placed, any hidden unit becomes unreliable and this process is experimentally known to improve the performance of the neural network (Srivastava et al., 2014).

2.6 Early stopping

Early stopping is an auto hyper-parameter algorithm to save training time and secure the good performance of the model. When training the model, the training error decreases gradually over time, yet the validation error increases. Then it would be better to stop the training at a point of the epoch process when the validation error is lowest (Goodfellow Yoshua Bengio et al., 2016). Patience method (Abadi et al., 2016) was considered to give the model on the training process the room for decreasing error even if the error does not decrease during some consecutive epochs. With the patience method, Early stopping will get the better-trained models with their weights saved at one specific epoch out of the others when the error did not decrease for a while and is the lowest. This process is also expected to shorten the training time as the training process stops before once the patience method is satisfied.

2.7 Loss function

Loss function is used to define the error in the training process. Mean Squared Error(MSE) has been widely chosen for the loss function in regression models. This is mainly due to: 1) MSE function is smooth and continuous, making Gradient Descent(GD) work well, 2) the gradient gets smaller near the minimum, 3) the algebra for the slope of GD is easy enough with MSE function(Rashid, 2016). MSE function is described in Formula (8):

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum (O - P)^2 \quad (8)$$

where P is the predicted value and O is the actual observed value; n is the number of data.

2.8 Optimizer

Optimizers are optimization algorithms employed for the GD method in DNN. In the GD method, once the loss function tells the degree of errors between predicted and observed values, then the gradient of the weight in the loss function, which is MSE in this paper, is calculated. The gradients of weights are vectors that decide where to step for the next optimization. Here, one important thing for the next optimization is to decide the size of the step, also known as the learning rate. In this paper, Adaptive Moment Estimation(Adam) is chosen as the optimizer. Adam is the adaptive optimizer, which it modifies its learning rate, and takes the strength of Momentum optimizer, which is a statistical approach to consider the weight of the past gradients and navigates the direction of GD(Goodfellow Yoshua Bengio et al., 2016; Kingma & Ba, 2015). The flowing reasons tell why Adam is used; 1) Experimentally, Adam suits well to solve non-convex optimization problems in the field of ML(Kingma & Ba, 2015), therefore is expected to find a global minimum in the sub dataset, which consists of the floodplain and the river channel with different ratios, 2) Its algorithm is available in Keras and Tensorflow.

3. Concepts of error indices

3.1 Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) is a quadratic index that calculates the average magnitude of the error. It is a scale-based error method, where the square root of the average of the squared difference between prediction and observation is estimated. The averaged errors are squared, and it has a high weight to large errors, compared to

MAE. The range is from 0 to ∞ , and lower values of RMSE are better. The mathematical expression of RMSE is described in Formula (9):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2} \quad (9)$$

where P is the predicted value and O is the observed value, and n is the number of data.

3.2 Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

Mean Absolute Error (MAE) is an index of the average magnitude of the absolute difference between prediction and observation. It is averaged with the number of data, and all the differences will have equal weight. The range is from 0 to ∞ , and lower values of MAE are better. The mathematical expression of MAE is described in Formula (10).

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |O_i - P_i| \quad (10)$$

where P is the predicted value and O is the observed value, and n is the number of data.

3.3 R^2

R^2 indicates the degree of collinearity between predicted and observed data. R^2 is the squared r , which is an index of standard regression and investigates the degree of the linear relationship. A value of zero means no correlation at all, whereas a value of 1 means that the dispersion of predicted values is equal to that of observed values. Thus, the range is from 0 to 1, and higher values of R^2 are better (Krause et al., 2005). R^2 is widely used in hydraulic modeling, playing a role as a benchmark for performance evaluation (Moriassi et al., 2015). The disadvantage of R^2 is the fact that it only concerns deviations, and it is not able to identify if a model predicts well or not. The model could have wrong predictions all time, yet the value of R^2 would be close to 1 (Krause et al., 2005).

$$R^2 = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})(P_i - \bar{P})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - \bar{P})^2}} \right]^2 \quad (11)$$

where P is the predicted value, \bar{P} is the average value of P , O is the observed value, and \bar{O} is the average value of O .

3.4 Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency Index (NSE)

Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency Index (NSE) is a normalized statistic that determines the degree of the residual variance, compared to measured data variance (Moriassi et al., 2015; Nash & Sutcliffe, 1970). The range lies between $-\infty$ to 1. When NSE index is lower than zero, the mean observed value is better than the predicted values from the model. Once NSE index reaches 1, it means the model has a perfect fit (Krause et al., 2005). It is commonly used as indices to evaluate the performance of hydrologic, hydraulic models. It is, however, not adequate to be used alone since NSE index might be close to the highest value even though a model performs badly. Other statistical tools, such as scatter plots may reveal important information that NSE cannot demonstrate (Jain & Sudheer, 2008).

$$NSE = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - P_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (O_i - \bar{O})^2} \quad (12)$$

where P is the predicted value, \bar{P} is the average value of P , O is the observed value, and \bar{O} is the average value of O .

3.5 Scatter Plots (SP)

Scatter Plots (SP) are employed to check the divergence from the 1:1 line, and they will provide a visual understanding of the behavior of the 1D CNN models (Moriassi et al., 2015). The inundation map produced by 1D CNN model will be 3D since it has 2D of spatial data with time series. All the predicted values are plotted in a single SP to visualize how the 1D CNN models behave as a whole. R^2 is employed to provide a statistical index.

4. References

- Abadi, M., Barham, P., Chen, J., Chen, Z., Davis, A., Dean, J., Devin, M., Ghemawat, S., Irving, G., Isard, M., Kudlur, M., Levenberg, J., Monga, R., Moore, S., Murray, D. G., Steiner, B., Tucker, P., Vasudevan, V., Warden, P., ... Zheng, X. (2016). TensorFlow: A system for large-scale machine learning. *Proceedings of the 12th USENIX Symposium on Operating Systems Design and Implementation, OSDI 2016*.
- Bai, S., Kolter, J. Z., & Koltun, V. (2018). *An Empirical Evaluation of Generic Convolutional and Recurrent Networks for Sequence Modeling*. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1803.01271>
- Gill, M. K., Asefa, T., Kaheil, Y., & McKee, M. (2007). Effect of missing data on performance of learning algorithms for hydrologic predictions: Implications to an imputation technique. *Water Resources Research*, 43(7), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006WR005298>
- Goodfellow Yoshua Bengio, I., Courville, A., Goodfellow, I., & Bengio, Y. (2016). *5 Deep Learning Title: Deep learning*. <https://lccn.loc.gov/2016022992>
- Ioffe, S., & Szegedy, C. (2015). Batch normalization: Accelerating deep network training by reducing internal covariate shift. *32nd International Conference on Machine Learning, ICML 2015, 1*, 448–456.
- Jain, S. K., & Sudheer, K. P. (2008). Fitting of hydrologic models: A close look at the nash-sutcliffe index. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering*, 13(10), 981–986. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1084-0699\(2008\)13:10\(981\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1084-0699(2008)13:10(981))
- Kingma, D. P., & Ba, J. L. (2015). Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. *3rd International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2015 - Conference Track Proceedings*, 1–15.
- Kiranyaz, S., Avci, O., Abdeljaber, O., Ince, T., Gabbouj, M., & Inman, D. J. (2019). *1D Convolutional Neural Networks and Applications: A Survey*. 1–20. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1905.03554>
- Krause, P., Boyle, D. P., & Bäse, F. (2005). Comparison of different efficiency criteria for hydrological model assessment. *Advances in Geosciences*, 5, 89–97. <https://doi.org/10.5194/adgeo-5-89-2005>
- Maas, A. L., Hannun, A. Y., & Ng, A. Y. (2013). Rectifier nonlinearities improve neural network acoustic models. *In ICML Workshop on Deep Learning for Audio, Speech and Language Processing*, 28.
- Moriasi, D. N., Gitau, M. W., Pai, N., & Daggupati, P. (2015). Hydrologic and water quality models: Performance measures and evaluation criteria. *Transactions of the ASABE*, 58(6), 1763–1785. <https://doi.org/10.13031/trans.58.10715>
- Nash, E., & Sutcliffe, V. (1970). *PART I- A DISCUSSION OF PRINCIPLES * The problem of determining river flows from rainfall, evaporation, and other factors, occupies a central place in the technology of applied hydrology. It is not only the essential problem of flood forecasting but a*. 10, 282–290.
- Rashid, T. (2016). *Make your own neural network: a gentle journey through the mathematics of neural networks, and making your own using the Python computer language*. CreateSpace, cop.
- Rautela, M., & Gopalakrishnan, S. (2020). *Deep Learning frameworks for wave propagation-based damage detection in Deep Learning frameworks for wave propagation-based damage detection in 1D-waveguides*. January, 1–11.
- Srivastava, N., Hinton, G., Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., & Salakhutdinov, R. (2014). Dropout: A simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*.
- Wang, S. H., Muhammad, K., Hong, J., Sangaiah, A. K., & Zhang, Y. D. (2020). Alcoholism identification via convolutional neural network based on parametric ReLU, dropout, and batch normalization. *Neural Computing and Applications*, 32(3), 665–680. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00521-018-3924-0>
- Wang, S. H., Phillips, P., Sui, Y., Liu, B., Yang, M., & Cheng, H. (2018). Classification of Alzheimer's Disease Based on

Eight-Layer Convolutional Neural Network with Leaky Rectified Linear Unit and Max Pooling. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 42(5), 85. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10916-018-0932-7>